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D 5.4 – COMMON TRAINING METHODOLOGY AND GUIDELINES

General information

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Definitions

Term	Description
Access Manager	The main contact for users and manager of the access provision at the level of the Research Infrastructure. The AM provide information to the users and redirect them to the appropriate <i>installation</i> (see below) of her/his RI
Installation Manager	The person, or group of persons, in charge of the management of the installation, and contact with the users for this specific installation
Installation	An installation is an elementary facility, that belongs to a RI, where all or part of the transnational access is effectively provided in the form of one or more services
Research Infrastructure	Facilities that provide resources and services for the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields. This definition includes the associated human resources, and it covers major equipment or sets of instruments; knowledge related facilities such as collections, archives or scientific data infrastructures; computing systems, communication networks, and any other infrastructure, of a unique nature and open to external users, essential to achieve excellence in research and innovation. Where relevant, they may be used beyond research, for example for education or public services, and they may be 'single-sited', 'virtual' or 'distributed' (from the EU Grant Agreement) ¹
Transnational Access	Access for users working in institutions from countries other than the country where access is granted unless access is provided by an ERIC or similar legal entity
Virtual Access	Access to online facilities such as .data and model, when no physical or remote access is required
Work Package	A set of related activities within a project

¹ For more information the reader is referred to the glossary in the [EU portal](#).

Acronyms

Acronyms	Full name
AgroServ	Integrated services supporting a sustainable agroecological transition
AM	Access Manager
IM	Installation Manager
I	Installation
RI	Research Infrastructure
TA	Transnational Access
VA	Virtual Access
WP	Work Package
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

Ensuring viable agroecological transitions towards sustainable and resilient agri-food systems

Agricultural land depletion, the loss of biodiversity and the growing scarcity of natural resources are some of the complex challenges we face in this century. Whether due to the competition for land use or due to the tensions on agricultural modes of production, the necessity to adapt our current agricultural production methods to continue producing agricultural goods while concomitantly maintaining, preserving, and adapting the ecosystems, is a necessity.

AgroServ was thus born from the need for a collective action capable of enhancing the sustainability of food systems and food chains while safeguarding human, animal, and environmental health and preserving natural resources and biodiversity and mitigating climate change. The project was launched to better align (scientific) approaches and capabilities, and more effectively and efficiently use resources to ensure a viable agroecological transition towards sustainable and resilient agri-food systems.

By bringing together several types of expertise, disciplines, and technologies, and by integrating the competence and know-how of ecologists, agronomists, biologists, chemists, bioengineers, analysts, social scientists, and economists, AgroServ is designed to advance our knowledge of agronomic and husbandry practices. While there is a focus on the threats and risks of agroecosystems, it simultaneously supports the development of new agroecological practices by fostering transdisciplinarity and integrating a socio-economic dimension in the offer to researchers.

1.2. Scope of the document

1.2.1. Task description

This deliverable will contribute towards the implementation of Task 5.3 (Joint training services for key end-users on operations from other WPs), which is dedicated to the organizational and developmental aspects of the AgroServ Training Programme. The need to develop a structured and innovative Training Programme within AgroServ arises from the unique challenges and opportunities posed by the nature of this project, which actively engages numerous stakeholders (D5.1) as well as converges multiple disciplines within the agroecological domain (D2.1).

Therefore, this task aims to elaborate a common methodology and provide guidance for the creation of training activities across all AgroServ Research Infrastructures and Work Packages.

The role of this task is crucial to maintain consistency and effectiveness in the training initiatives within the AgroServ project.

The common methodology serves as a linchpin by:

- i. offering a structured framework to streamline the development of training activities in AgroServ;
- ii. guaranteeing harmonization with the overarching goals and objectives of AgroServ RIs;
- iii. improving the efficiency of knowledge exchange and creating a cohesive learning experience for participants;
- iv. enhancing the impact and success of the training efforts within the diverse landscape of AgroServ RIs.

To achieve this goal, in a collaborative initiative involving both RIs and WP Leaders, a comprehensive assessment of the training requirements for users was conducted. The data gathered through this survey served as the basis for estimating the current collective training needs.

1.2.2. Objectives of the document

The purpose of this deliverable is to:

- detail the structure of the AgroServ Training Programme ensuring alignment with relevant target groups' needs and the training initiatives already planned within involved WPs and RIs;
- provide trainers, including Access Managers, Installation Managers, and WP Leaders, with a common methodology and guidance for the development of the training activities in every RI/I;
- ensure efficient training coordination to guarantee that the community of users receives the needed support to apply, access and use the AgroServ RI services.

1.2.3. Structure of the document

The deliverable is structured in 5 sections:

- **Section 1** – Introduces the context of the deliverable, its scope, structure and interactions with other WPs and initiatives;

- **Section 2** – Presents the complexity, the challenges and the importance of a standardized Training Programme. Presents the results of the training needs evaluation conducted within AgroServ Access managers and WP leaders;
- **Section 3** – Describes the Training Programme planned within the AgroServ project, its structure and objectives;
- **Section 4** – Focuses on the description of a common methodology for the development of the training activities within AgroServ;
- **Section 5** – Provides guidelines for the development of training activities in AgroServ.

1.2.4. Interactions with other Work Packages and Initiatives

Since D 5.4 contributes towards the implementation of T5.3 which deals with the whole AgroServ Training Programme (including WPs and RIs), it relies, by nature, on constant interaction with other AgroServ Work Packages.

Firstly, the training sessions will address subjects specific to certain AgroServ tasks. This includes the utilization of the portfolio of research infrastructure services (T1.1 - *Set up and maintain the user access portal*), transdisciplinary approach (T2.2 - *Developing AgroServ transdisciplinary approach supporting the Access Framework*), the use of integrated services (T2.3 - *Service pipelines clustering*), in integrated data management and models (T3.3, T3.4, T3.5 - *Consolidating integrated data management and analysis services*), addressing ethical and legal considerations (T4.3 - *Ethical and legal issues relevant to services provision*), and developing skills, competencies, and methodologies, such as stakeholder engagement and co-creation techniques, essential for effective participation in Living Labs (T6.1 - *Joint training services for key end-users on operations from other WPs*).

Secondly, these guidelines will be also used while delivering training activities for Access Managers (T2.4 - *Building a knowledge base for access managers on cross-cutting service pipelines and service customisation*).

Thirdly, these guidelines have been formulated relying on the outcomes derived from Task 5.1 - *Build a transdisciplinary community of users*. The identification of the target audience and the classification of key end-users were informed by the data presented in D5.1.

Finally, to design an advanced and tailored Training Programme, best practices and innovative training methodologies from other pertinent training initiatives such as RiTrain and RiTrain Plus have been incorporated. Additionally, we have identified and established synergies with other training initiatives, leveraging insights from T5.2 - *Clustering and Liaising with other relevant initiatives and projects*. This approach aims to ensure the development of a cutting-edge Programme that benefits from the collective knowledge and experiences of diverse training initiatives in the field.

2. The Importance of a Common Methodology for the Development of Training Activities in AgroServ

AgroServ unites 11 RIs (Figure 1) with a shared goal of establishing an integrated, cohesive, interdisciplinary, and interoperable network of RIs to support sustainable and resilient agriculture, fostering agroecological transitions throughout Europe. The project spans diverse domains—life sciences, environmental sciences, chemistry, biotechnologies, information sciences and social sciences—collaborating to leverage advancements and enhance interoperability among RIs and domains.

Figure 1. The RIs at the Core of AgroServ

Within this context, it is essential to create and design a common, structured, and innovative Training Programme that considers and bridges the diverse expertise, research methodologies, and state-of-the-art knowledge in each discipline involved, while also considering the various types of stakeholders.

The subsequent requirements underscore the importance of a harmonized Training Programme:

- **Diversity of Scientific Backgrounds**

Researchers involved in AgroServ come from a variety of scientific backgrounds, including agriculture, ecology, technology, and social sciences. A structured Training Programme should cater to the diverse knowledge base, ensuring that participants acquire a

comprehensive understanding of relevant concepts and methodologies from different disciplines.

- **Transdisciplinary Collaboration**

AgroServ requires collaboration across disciplinary boundaries to address complex agro-ecological challenges. The Training Programme should emphasize transdisciplinary skills, fostering effective communication and collaboration among researchers with different expertise to facilitate a holistic approach to problem-solving.

- **Integration of Research Methodologies**

Researchers bring various research methodologies, such as field experiments, data modeling and socio-economic analyses. The Training Programme should integrate these methodologies, ensuring researchers can leverage a spectrum of approaches to address multifaceted agroecological issues and produce robust and comprehensive outcomes.

- **Innovation and Technological Integration**

AgroServ involves different technological solutions for data management, integrated services, and models. The Training Programme must incorporate innovative technologies, ensuring researchers are proficient in utilizing advanced tools and platforms essential for the project's success.

- **Stakeholder Engagement and Co-Creation**

AgroServ emphasizes stakeholder engagement and co-creation methodologies. The Training Programme should equip researchers with skills to engage with diverse stakeholders effectively. This includes understanding local contexts, collaborating with farmers, and incorporating end-user's perspectives into research activities.

- **Ethical and Legal Considerations**

Ethical and legal aspects are integral, especially when dealing with data management and socio-economic studies. The Training Programme should address ethical considerations, data privacy, and legal frameworks, ensuring researchers conduct their work responsibly and in compliance with relevant regulations.

- **Continuous Learning and Adaptability**

Given the dynamic nature of agroecological research, researchers must be adaptable and open to continuous learning. The Training Programme should boost a culture of continuous learning, encouraging researchers to stay updated on emerging trends, methodologies, and technologies relevant to their field of study.

To conclude, AgroServ should offer unparalleled training opportunities and serve as a pivotal educational and upskilling platform for supporting the next generation of scientists, both access /installation managers and users. Users of RIs benefit from comprehensive technical support and training, enabling them to acquire proficiency in utilizing advanced technologies, conducting data analysis, and ensuring quality control. Additionally, it is imperative to provide comprehensive training and skill development for RI personnel at all levels, ranging from top management to technicians and support staff. Investing in the training of RI managers,

operators, and users significantly contributes to the success of RIs and optimizes their utilization (ESFRI-WHITE Paper 2020)².

3. Training Needs Assessment

In collaboration with RI's access managers and WP leaders, a training needs assessment has been undertaken to identify the gaps in skills and knowledge, ensuring a targeted (or tailored) AgroServ Training Programme aligned with AgroServ's objectives. Two online surveys have been sent employing the LimeSurvey tool³ to access managers and WP leaders (see Annex).

Access Managers survey: the purpose of this survey was to assess best practices and Training Programmes already in place at RIs, while also collaboratively evaluating the potential training needs of both our users and access managers. The survey consisted of a total of 18 questions (14 open-ended questions and 4 multiple choices) (see Annex).

WP leaders survey: the purpose of this survey was to assess the planned training activities across various Work Packages (WPs) of the AgroServ project and collaboratively evaluate the potential training needs of our users. The survey consisted of 14 questions (11 open-ended questions and 3 multiple choices) (see Annex).

3.1. Results

3.1.1. Access Managers

The survey saw nearly complete participation from access RI managers representing 5 RIs indicating a robust level of engagement throughout the community. Virtually every access manager involved with the RIs contributed to the survey, emphasizing the widespread interest and importance placed on gathering insights and feedback. This extensive participation underscores the significance of the survey findings, as they reflect a comprehensive perspective encompassing diverse viewpoints and experiences from access managers across various RIs. Such widespread involvement not only bolsters the credibility and reliability of the survey results but also underscores the collective commitment of access managers toward improving the effectiveness and efficiency of Research Infrastructures.

²chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.esfri.eu/sites/default/files/White_paper_ESFRI-final.pdf

³ www.livesurvey.com

Training Activities Planned in RIs

Through the survey, we have successfully pinpointed key areas for improvement and innovation within the RIs. Training Programmes already planned within RIs including best practices and innovative ideas have been collected (Table 1). Among the training activities already in place, the topics range from technical (such as *in-vitro* culture, plant imaging, digital platforms, etc.) to those transversals to AgroServ, such as application procedures and services. These training sessions will involve different target groups, both internal and external to AgroServ and will be delivered in various formats.

Table 1 Planned Training Activities within the AgroServ RIs

RI	TOPICS	TARGET GROUPS	FORMAT	DURATION	WHEN
AnaEE-ERIC	High-tech installation/platform	Installation Managers, users	Both	1-3 hrs (online) 1-3 days (F2F)	tbd
	Topics related to the measurement of greenhouse gas emissions in the ecosystem	Installation Managers, researchers,	Face-to-face	16 hrs	tbd
MIRRI-ERIC	In-vitro culture of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi	Scientists, students, technicians, industry	Face-to-face	40 hrs	10-14th June 2024
EMPHASIS	Information about AgroServ, Process of applications and Transdisciplinarity	Access Managers, Installation Managers	Online	2 hrs	After launching a call
EURO-BIOIMAGING ERIC	Plant imaging and different imaging techniques with relevance for Agroecology	Researchers	Both	1-3 hrs (online) 3-5 days (F2F)	During 2024

EU- OPENSREEN ERIC	Drug discovery	External scientists, staff	Both	1-2 hrs (online) 3-14 days (F2F)	Once per year
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Access Managers and Users' Needs Identification

The survey also aimed to identify the training needs of users within the AgroServ project. By soliciting feedback and insights from 11 Access Managers, we sought to gain a comprehensive understanding of the specific skills, knowledge gaps, and learning requirements. The results from the survey are expressed as percentage frequency distribution. Access Managers identified as their main need as being deep knowledge about AgroServ services (40%) followed by Data Management, Communication Skills and Transdisciplinary Approach (13% each) and the remaining, i.e. Tools and Platforms, Agroecology, Application Procedure and Open Innovation (7% each). Specifically in relation to AgroServ services, AM expressed their need to get a deeper understanding of other RIs services in order to guarantee integration and customization of services across RIs and cross/transdisciplinarity. On the other hand, AM identified users' main needs as being integration of data and models, selection of AgroServ services (30 % each), transdisciplinary approach (20%) followed by successful proposal writing and submission, integration of services and ethical issues (10% each). At installation level, AM identified as the main need of TAVA users as being the use of instrument (41%), laboratory safety procedure (29%), laboratory waste management, sample preparation followed by data management, data policy and metadata analysis (6% each) (Figure 2). This approach allowed us also to gather experience from AgroServ RIs' Access Managers and enabled us to consider needs from various disciplines and thus support users to maximize the effectiveness and utilization of AgroServ services. By addressing needs, we can ensure that training activities will be tailored to the various target groups under the AgroServ Training Programme, ultimately enhancing their ability to leverage AgroServ resources for their research and innovation endeavors.

Which skills and knowledge do Access Managers need?

Which skills and knowledge do you think users need?

Which training should the Installation Manager provide to TAVA users?

Figure 2. Needs Assessment Survey Results (results expressed as percentage frequency distribution)

3.1.2. WP Leaders

Each WP Leader participated in the survey and provided valuable feedback and contributions to collect and frame the activities foreseen within the AgroServ project. For each WP, topics, target group, format, duration and tentative date have been identified, as outlined in Table 2. This preliminary identification serves as a foundation for planning and organizing the training initiatives, providing guidelines for subsequent development and implementation. As the project progresses and additional information becomes available, these details will be further refined and finalized to ensure alignment with the objectives and timelines of each WP.

Table 2. Planned Training Activities within the AgroServ RIs

WP	TOPICS	TARGET GROUPS	FORMAT	DURATION	WHEN
1	How to deal with the application process and platform	Access Managers, AgroServ partners, users	Online	1-3 hrs	Monthly
	Practical execution of the TA activities	Access Managers, AgroServ partners, users	Face-to-face	Depending on the access	Upon the access
2	Transdisciplinary approach How to use the catalogue How to integrate the services	Access Managers, Installation Managers	Online	1-3 hrs	tbd
	Topics identified in this survey				
3	Capacity building about using RDM tools and available resources	TAVA users or potential users	Online	tbd	Upon project acceptance

5	Co-creation	Access Managers, Installation Managers	Online	1 hr	Tbd (to be agreed on the need)
8	Communication tools and strategies	AgroServ partners Newcomers within WP8	1. Face-to-face 2. online	1. 16 hours (4h/day) 2. 1 hour	1. January 2025, WP8 2. February 2025, WP1-9

4. The AgroServ Training Programme

4.1. Target groups

The AgroServ project seeks to engage diverse stakeholders from various sectors and disciplines. In D5.1, two distinct groups of stakeholders have already been identified, as illustrated in Figure 3. Firstly, there is a wide array of stakeholders within the AgroServ Ecosystem community, encompassing individuals, organizations, or institutions with an interest in AgroServ and the services provided by its RIs and installations. This group stands to potentially benefit from the project's outcomes, and our strategy involves ensuring long-term sustainability by fostering synergies through activities such as knowledge-sharing, consultation, partnership, and dissemination of AgroServ activities.

Figure 3. Stakeholders Group Definition in AgroServ Project (from D5.1)

The primary focus of AgroServ is its user community, comprising individuals who will directly utilize its services through the AgroServ call for applications. This community represents the main target audience for AgroServ's efforts to enhance Agroecology research hence, should benefit from various training activities conducted within AgroServ research infrastructures (RIs). Within this group, we have identified two distinct user categories within which training programmes will be designed: **end users** and **prospective users**.

End users (or TA/VA users) are those who have active and direct access to the services provided by AgroServ RIs, who applied to the call submitted a full research proposal and successfully went through the selection process. On the other hand, prospective users encompass scientists interested in agroecology and AgroServ RIs, who intend to apply and follow the project initiatives.

Recognizing the importance of catering to both groups, our training initiatives are designed to address the diverse needs and requirements of prospective users and end users alike. By providing tailored training sessions, we aim to provide both groups with the necessary skills, knowledge, and resources to effectively engage with and benefit from the AgroServ project, thereby maximizing its impact and relevance within the agroecological community.

In addition to focusing on users, the AgroServ Training Programme will also target Access Managers, as outlined in T2.4. Therefore, the Training Programme will include provisions tailored specifically for Access Managers, recognizing their pivotal role in facilitating user access to AgroServ RI services. Guidelines and training materials will be formulated to equip Access Managers with the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively manage access procedures, support users, and ensure smooth operation of the RI services. Besides, AgroServ aims to enhance its capabilities and foster a cohesive framework for seamless service delivery and user support.

4.2. Programme Structure and Objectives

In developing the AgroServ Training Programme, we have drawn upon the best practices observed in various training initiatives, including Ritrain Plus⁴ and insights gathered from our survey. By leveraging these resources and incorporating feedback from diverse stakeholders, we aim to create a comprehensive and tailored Training Programme that addresses the specific needs and preferences of our user community. Furthermore, we aspire to foster collaboration with other projects, integrate various methodologies, emphasize technological proficiency, and instil ethical and stakeholder-centric practices to ensure the success of this multifaceted research initiative. By pooling resources and expertise, we can maximize the impact and effectiveness of our training efforts, ultimately empowering users to make optimal

⁴ Please refer to the Training Platform and Community of Practices under <https://ritrainplus.eu/>

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use of AgroServ resources for advancing agricultural research and innovation. Regarding AgroServ, we are considering implementing three distinct levels of training. These levels will be structured around project-specific topics and target groups, although we intend for them to remain flexible and adaptable.

The training activity at **Research Infrastructure Level** will engage both potential and end-users plus a broader community of stakeholders, as highlighted in D5.1. These initiatives will be strategically designed to precede the launch of the call, primarily aimed at providing users with all the information and support in the application procedure or use of the catalogue of services. These sessions will empower participants with the necessary skills and “transversal” knowledge to effectively utilize RI resources and seamlessly integrate services into their research workflows. Therefore, investing in Training Programmes that address transversal topics is not only beneficial for individual professional development but also instrumental in driving overall organizational growth and competitiveness. This training will be mainly delivered virtually – as a workshop or webinar - to reach as many users as possible and maximize the impact of AgroServ training initiatives. At this level, mainly Access Managers and WP Leaders will be in charge of carrying out the training according to the expertise and role in the project.

At the **Installation Level**, training activities will focus on engaging Transnational Access (TA/VA) users during their access to AgroServ Research Infrastructure (RI) services. These on-the-job training sessions will delve into topics that are specific to the expertise and focus of the RI, ensuring that users are well-prepared and equipped to utilize the services they have accessed. Given the immediate relevance and timing of these sessions, they will primarily be conducted face-to-face, coinciding with the user's access to the services. This approach aims to provide personalized guidance and support tailored training to the user's needs and the specific services they are utilizing. However, considering the diverse nature of access arrangements, virtual delivery of these training sessions will also be available when necessary. Installation Managers will bear the responsibility for orchestrating and conducting these training sessions, ensuring that users are proficient and confident in utilizing the RI services effectively. The coordinator and mentor of the local staff of the involved RIs will be assigned to each user providing the primary link between users and local staff. The mentors will assist the users to: i) discuss design and agree on experiment details; ii) train the users in standard operating procedures applicable to the installations; iii) oversee the daily planning of the experiment including data processing and analysis, iv) assists data interpretation including the preparation of manuscripts and reports as required and appropriate.

At the **Project level**, the primary focus of training initiatives will center on Access Managers, with delivery predominantly conducted online. The training content will be curated to encompass a comprehensive understanding of all aspects of the project, ensuring Access Managers and Installation Managers are well-versed in project goals, procedures, and

overarching objectives. Furthermore, the training topics will be designed to cultivate a new generation of Access Managers, drawing inspiration from best practices and strategies such as those outlined by ESFRI⁵ or initiatives like Ritrain Plus⁶. By equipping access managers with a thorough understanding of project dynamics and fostering the development of new managerial skills, the training endeavors at the project level to optimize the efficiency and effectiveness of access management processes within AgroServ, aligning with stakeholders' perspectives and fostering continuous improvement.

Our overarching aim is to create a collaborative and innovative Programme that can accommodate the diverse needs of our participants. While the delineation between these levels may not be rigidly enforced, this approach will enable us to offer tailored learning experiences that suit the varying expertise levels and interests of our users. By organizing training sessions in this manner, we seek to promote collaboration and knowledge-sharing among participants, ensuring that everyone receives training that aligns with their unique roles and objectives within the AgroServ project.

5. Common Methodology for the Development of the Training Activities in AgroServ

In all types of training, there is always a learner who is required to learn something. What exactly should the target groups under the AgroServ Training Programme learn?

Since 1956 when B. Bloom described knowledge, skills and attitudes as 'Bloom's Taxonomies', the three learning dimensions of *knowledge*, *skills* and *attitudes* have been considered central in all types of training. It is not enough for learners *to know (knowledge)* but they should also be able *to act (skills)* because of the knowledge they have acquired. Besides transmitting necessary knowledge to deliver an appointed task, there has been a growing focus on ensuring that trainees also have the *confidence to do it (attitudes)*.

Trainees might leave the training sessions with high proficiency in the technical subject behind the task, but low confidence in performing it and this has consequences for the overall efficiency of the training.⁷

⁵ ESFRI ROADMAP (forthcoming), ESFRI, WHITE PAPER, Report on Access to Research Infrastructures and Charter on Access to RIs Dec 2023 at <https://zenodo.org/records/10555986>.

⁶ <https://ritrainplus.eu/course-catalogue/>

⁷ Z-Fact0r D7.2 Report on training activities

<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5cdb248e0&appId=PPGMS>

For that purpose, trainers should ensure that the training environment, methodology and methods (how) all point in that direction, i.e. addressing all those three learning dimensions.

5.1. A Principled Training Environment

As a start, trainers should ensure that basic principles and common rules are adhered to, i.e.:

- **Participation and empowerment**

They go hand in hand and are very much interlinked in their application. Applying this principle means that trainers should place trainees' knowledge and experience at the center and regard those as the starting point in the training session and by using examples that are close to their research interests. It also entails that trainers should apply a participatory approach by engaging participants as much as possible in the learning/teaching process by using interactive methods and techniques. The ultimate goal of the trainers is, of course, to empower trainees with the necessary skills and "transversal" knowledge to effectively utilize RI resources and seamlessly integrate services into their research workflows.

- **Accountability**

Applying this principle means both trainers and trainees have a responsibility to meet the objectives of the training. In other words, both are *accountable* for that. As for the trainers, it entails relating those objectives to the target group's needs by reflecting those in the training and adjusting the training accordingly, if required. A context analysis (step 1 below) may already guide them in that respect but may not be sufficient. So, conducting a more specific needs assessment before each training is crucial to further guide trainers into tailoring the training to the target group's needs. Trainers should also consider creating the right environment for trainees and should be made accountable through ongoing evaluations. As for the trainees, it entails showing engagement in all the above-mentioned processes by actively participating in needs assessments, evaluations, etc.

- **Non-discrimination/Equality and Inclusion**

Applying this principle entails considering how to establish a *diverse* target group, *leaving no one behind*. This in turn entails establishing *fair* selection criteria, i.e., criteria that are regardless of participants' gender, age, race, religion, etc. ensuring that invitation to those trainings reaches out to disadvantaged groups, e.g., researchers from countries where research does not receive sufficient financial support but also equal access in terms of allocated time proportion to research facilities is guaranteed to those researchers. This means, for instance, providing an inclusive environment enabling all users to access relevant RIs/lis, preventing any discriminatory behaviours that may arise during any training activity; developing gender-sensitive training activities by, for instance, making training schedules and

arrangements flexible enough to suit parents with young children, in particular breast-feeding mothers, planning for the use of gender-inclusive language and methods. Trainers should also consider familiarizing themselves with the concept of non-violent communication (Korlipara and Shah 2022)⁸, while also planning to transfer that concept to participants to enable them to adhere to the same rules of communication; planning for participatory and inclusive activities during the execution of training such as group work and energisers.

5.2. A Participatory and Interactive Methodology

From a methodological perspective, applying the above-mentioned principles will translate into the use of a learner-centered methodology which entails, as suggested by its name, that the actual participants are *at the center* of the learning/training experience. Trainers and all staff involved in the conceptualization of the training including both planning and designing which is the focus of this deliverable will have to take training participants' needs and interests into account. What participants will have to learn will have to be meaningful to them and they should be taking an active role in the learning/training process.

The Learning Pyramid concept (Figure 4), often attributed to the National Training Laboratory in Bethel, Maine, suggests that individuals retain information more effectively through active teaching methods rather than passive ones. According to this model, learners retain only a small fraction of information through lectures or passive reading, whereas they retain significantly more through practice by doing, group discussion, and teaching others. While the exact figures presented in the learning pyramid have been debated and scrutinized for their accuracy, the underlying principle underscores the importance of engaging learners in active participation and hands-on experiences to enhance learning outcomes. This idea has profound implications for training designers, emphasizing the need to incorporate interactive and experiential learning methods into training activities to optimize knowledge retention and skill acquisition.

⁸ “The NVC concept provides scope for empathetic understanding and awareness of the needs of others involved and, thus, opens pathways for mutually respectful dialogue” Korlipara, M., & Shah, H. (2022). “Power of words”: impact, concerns and applications of nonviolent communication training. *European Journal of Training and Development*.

Figure 4. Learning Pyramid

To adhere to the above-mentioned principles and methodology, within the suggested guidelines for the development of training activities under AgroServ, we will propose a wide range of interactive training methods from which trainers can choose or may, in some instances, use in combination based on their respective training context.

6. Guidelines for the Development of the Training Activities in AgroServ

To ensure its effectiveness and relevance to participants' needs, training activities under the AgroServ Training Programme, just as any other training activity or project, will require trainers and all relevant staff involved to undergo a systematic process, a “cycle” involving four different stages or phases from *planning* to *design* to *delivery* and finally, *follow up* (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Training Cycle Diagram⁹

As the deliverable aims at providing practical guidance for the *development* of training activities, in this section we will focus on the first and second phase of this cycle. Both these two phases require careful planning and consideration of various factors. Those factors are described below as steps that the trainer will have to undertake towards the development of effective training activities tailored to participants' needs.

6.1. Guidelines for Training Planning

Step 1: Context Analysis

A context analysis for the AgroServ Training Programme and all training activities included therein has already been carried out and the conclusions are relevant for any future training course or workshop. That said, to get further insights into the relevance of the individual training course/workshop at the specific RI/Project level, a one-step deeper analysis might be required. For that purpose, trainers should consider the following questions:

Why are you going to do this training in this RI/Project or at the Project level?

What other activities/training activities is this training part of? What's the relationship?

⁹ From Planning to Impact: A Manual on Human Rights Training Methodology (2020) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.18356/33ef5d5d-en>

Step 2: Identify target groups and their needs

Assess the target groups to understand their backgrounds, skill levels, and learning preferences, which will inform the design and delivery of the training. Conducting a comprehensive target group analysis involves several steps. Firstly, gather demographic information such as age, education level, job role and experience. This helps to understand the diverse backgrounds of the participants. Secondly, assess their existing knowledge and skills related to the training topic through surveys, pre-assessments, or interviews. This provides insight into the starting point of the participants and allows for the customization of training content accordingly. Additionally, consider their learning preferences, such as preferred learning styles, formats, and delivery methods. Engage with stakeholders and key personnel to gain insights into the participants' expectations, challenges, and specific training objectives. By thoroughly analyzing the target group, trainers can tailor the training content, materials, and delivery methods to effectively address the diverse needs and skill levels of participants, ultimately maximizing the impact and relevance of the Training Programme, trainers should consider several questions to gain insights into the audience's expectations and needs:

What is the anticipated attendance?

What are the participants' aspirations and anticipations for the training?

What apprehensions or worries might they have?

What variety of backgrounds, expertise, age groups, genders, and professional positions might be encompassed within the audience?

Step 3: Practical and logistical context

Get an overview of the timing and duration, number of participants and the venue/delivery modality of the training/workshop depending among others on the allocated funds for the activity within your RI/I or at the project level.

The number of participants requires careful consideration as it should not be too high, i.e. involving 10 to 15 participants, to adhere to the abovementioned and described principle of participation and empowerment hence, be able to apply a participatory and interactive methodology and related methods for effective learning.

Delivering training effectively requires careful consideration of the most suitable delivery methods based on factors such as audience needs, content complexity, and logistical constraints. In the AgroServ Programme, we have also to consider the level at which the training is performed and the type of users.

Two types of delivery can be distinguished, each with its advantages. *Web-based training*, whether synchronous or asynchronous, offers flexibility and accessibility, while *in-person training* provides opportunities for immediate interaction and hands-on experiences.

Web-based training, Driscoll and Tomiak (2000)¹⁰ whether synchronous (real-time) or asynchronous (self-paced), leverages online platforms to deliver content to remote participants. Synchronous web-based training allows for real-time interaction between participants and instructors through features like live video conferencing, chat rooms, and instant messaging. This format is ideal for facilitating discussions, group activities, and Q&A sessions, providing a sense of immediacy and connection despite physical distance. Asynchronous web-based training, on the other hand, allows participants to access training materials and complete activities at their own pace, providing flexibility for individuals with varying schedules and time zones. While lacking real-time interaction, asynchronous training accommodates diverse learning preferences and enables participants to revisit content as needed.

The suggested tools to use for delivering this type of training are:

- Miro
- Zoom
- Mural
- Jamboard
- Google meet

There are distinct benefits associated with both web-based and in-person training delivery methods. Web-based training, whether synchronous or asynchronous, provides flexibility by allowing participants to access materials at their convenience, regardless of location or time zone. This format accommodates diverse schedules and learning preferences, making it particularly suitable for individuals with busy lifestyles or those who prefer self-paced learning. Additionally, web-based training enhances accessibility by eliminating the need for participants to travel to a specific location, reducing associated costs and logistical challenges.

On the other hand, *in-person training* offers unique advantages, particularly in terms of fostering immediate interaction and hands-on experiences. Face-to-face sessions facilitate real-time communication and collaboration among participants and instructors, enabling dynamic discussions, group activities, and personalized feedback. In-person training also provides opportunities for participants to engage in practical exercises, simulations, and demonstrations, allowing for immersive learning experiences that may be more challenging to replicate in virtual environments. Furthermore, the interpersonal connections formed during in-person training sessions contribute to a sense of community and camaraderie among participants, enriching the overall learning experience.

Within in-presence learning, different approaches can be applied:

- **On-the-job learning** involves acquiring new skills and knowledge through hands-on experience and practical application in real work situations. This approach allows

¹⁰ Driscoll, M., & Tomiak, G. R. (2000). Web-based training: Using technology to design adult learning experiences.

individuals to learn by doing, gaining valuable insights and expertise that may not be easily attained through traditional classroom-based training. By immersing themselves in authentic work tasks and projects, participants develop problem-solving abilities, adaptability, and confidence in their abilities, all of which are essential for success in their roles.

- **Mentoring** provides a personalized approach to learning and development by pairing individuals with experienced professionals who serve as guides, advisors, and role models (Harvey et. al, 2017)¹¹. Mentors offer guidance, support, and constructive feedback, helping mentees navigate challenges, set goals, and enhance their skills and knowledge. Through one-on-one interactions and mentorship relationships, participants benefit from personalized attention, tailored learning experiences, and opportunities for professional growth and advancement. Mentoring also fosters a sense of accountability and belonging, as mentees receive ongoing support and encouragement from their mentors.
- **Collaborative training** (Yang, 2023)¹² brings together individuals from diverse backgrounds, disciplines, and perspectives to learn and work together toward common goals. This approach encourages teamwork, communication, and collaboration, as participants collaborate on projects, solve problems, and share knowledge and expertise. Collaborative training leverages the collective intelligence and creativity of participants, fostering innovation, idea generation, and continuous improvement. By working collaboratively, participants develop essential teamwork and interpersonal skills, expand their professional networks, and gain exposure to different ways of thinking and working. In conclusion, on-the-job learning, mentoring, and collaborative training represent invaluable assets for nurturing professional growth, extending benefits to both our users and RI access managers. These endeavors are instrumental in shaping a new generation of scientists who are proficient in integrating various scientific disciplines into their research endeavors and adept at addressing essential responsibilities often overlooked by scientists, including ethical guidelines' adherence and effective data management.
- **Hybrid approaches or “blended learning”** - Tayebinik and Puteh (2013)¹³ often hailed as a dynamic and versatile educational approach, seamlessly integrates traditional face-to-face instruction with online learning components. This innovative method combines the best of both worlds, offering learners flexibility, interactivity, and personalized experiences. By leveraging a mix of in-person classroom sessions, virtual lectures, interactive modules, and self-paced online activities, blended learning caters to diverse learning styles and preferences. Participants benefit from the convenience of accessing course materials remotely while still enjoying the benefits of real-time interaction and collaboration during in-person sessions. Blended learning encourages active engagement, fosters independent

¹¹ Harvey, M., Ambler, T., & Cahir, J. (2017). Spectrum approach to mentoring: An evidence-based approach to mentoring for academics working in higher education. *Teacher development*, 21(1), 160-174.

¹² Yang, X. (2023). A historical review of collaborative learning and cooperative learning. *TechTrends*, 67(4), 718-728.

¹³ Tayebinik, M., & Puteh, M. (2013). Blended Learning or E-learning? arXiv preprint arXiv:1306.4085.

learning, and enhances knowledge retention by providing a rich and interactive learning environment that adapts to the unique needs of each learner. Ultimately, blended learning empowers individuals to take control of their learning journey, promoting deeper understanding, skill development, and lifelong learning habits.

To get further insights into practical and logistical issues, trainers should consider the following:

When how long?

How many participants?

Venue/delivery modality?

Step 4: Define clear learning objectives

The first step is to define clear learning objectives for the training, outlining what participants should be able to *know* and *do* by the end of the training. It is a crucial step in ensuring its effectiveness and relevance to the intended audience. By clearly defining the goals and objectives of the training, trainers can pinpoint the specific knowledge, skills, and attitudes/behaviors they aim to address. Moreover, aligning the training objectives with organizational goals, i.e. the RIs/Is ensures that training contributes to broader strategic objectives and addresses pressing organizational needs. That in turn, can contribute to the sustainability of the training within the individual RIs/Is. To get insights into the objectives of the training, trainers should consider the following questions:

What do you want to achieve with this training?

What knowledge, skills and attitudes/behaviours should participants develop?

6.2. Guidelines for Training Design

Step 5: Decide on the topic/s, format/module and material

Select topics, and design a Programme and agenda. Choose proper instructional materials and tools, such as presentations, handouts, videos, or interactive modules, to support the learning process. Consider FAIR-ification of training material incorporating FAIR principles, i.e., findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability already within the design process to avoid unnecessary duplication of work across AgroServ (Skills4EOSC, 2023)¹⁴. Interoperability entails that training material should be designed so that it can be used in multiple learning/training environments. Reusability entails that the training material should

¹⁴ Skills4EOSC; Skills for the European Open Science Commons: Creating a Training Ecosystem for Open and FAIR Science, D2.3 Community-endorsed quality assurance and certification framework for professional training and qualifications;
<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e500c73246&appId=PPGMS>

be designed so that it is reusable by both other trainers and trainees and that it can be repurposed for different learning contexts. Consider technology requirements, to ensure a smooth delivery of the training. Also consider delivering relevant material in stages, i.e., *before* the training (see pre-readings), *during* the actual implementation of the training (to support the training process) and *after* (post-readings to reinforce/wrap/up the acquired competence). To get further insights into the content, format and material issues, trainers should consider the following questions:

Which topics, issues and relevant activities should be included in the Training Programme?

Which format would be best suited to address the defined topics, issues and activities? Develop a plan/Programme.

Which material would be best suited to address the defined topics and which material to distribute before, during and after the training respectively?

Step 6: Select proper training methods

This step requires careful consideration of various factors such as the specific learning objectives, specific target group's needs, complexity of the content, time and logistical constraints including whether the training will be conducted in a single session or multiple sessions over a period of time, and whether it will be conducted in-person, online, or through a blended approach. Based on all those considerations, choose the most appropriate methods. By carefully identifying proper methods for the training, trainers can design activities that effectively meet the learning needs of participants and achieve the desired learning outcomes.

In light of the above-described guiding principles and methodology, several methods are recommended from which trainers can choose from/apply in combination in order to foster acquisition and retention¹⁵, i.e. Table 3:

• Pre-readings

Pre-readings serve as a foundational element in training programmes by providing participants with essential background information and key concepts related to the training topic. These materials may include relevant articles, reports, or summaries that offer an overview of the subject matter. By encouraging participants to engage with pre-readings before attending training sessions, they have the opportunity to familiarize themselves with the fundamental principles and terminology associated with the topic. This preliminary exposure primes participants for deeper understanding during the training sessions, as they enter with a basic level of knowledge and context. Pre-readings also promote active learning by prompting participants to critically analyse and reflect on the material independently, enhancing their comprehension and retention of information. Additionally, pre-readings can facilitate more meaningful discussions and interactions during training

¹⁵ See Table 3 for a quick overview of recommended participatory methods.

sessions, as participants can build upon their prior knowledge and engage in more nuanced discussions. Overall, pre-readings play a crucial role in laying the groundwork for effective learning experiences, enabling participants to make the most of their training opportunities and achieve greater mastery of the subject matter.

- **Short lectures**

They provide concise yet informative overviews, ensuring essential information is delivered efficiently. Very short lectures are designed to efficiently deliver essential information concisely, maximizing the effectiveness of training sessions. Unlike traditional lectures, which can be lengthy and exhaustive, very short lectures focus on distilling key concepts and insights into brief presentations. This format allows trainers to capture participants' attention and maintain engagement by delivering information clearly and succinctly. By emphasizing only the most crucial points, very short lectures help to streamline the learning process and prevent information overload. Participants benefit from receiving a concentrated dose of information that is easy to digest and retain, facilitating quicker comprehension and assimilation of new knowledge. Additionally, the brevity of these lectures enables trainers to cover a wider range of topics within a limited time frame, maximizing the efficiency of training sessions. Overall, very short lectures serve as effective tools for delivering essential information efficiently, ensuring that training sessions are engaging, informative, and productive.

- **Case studies**

Case studies are a powerful instructional tool that immerses participants in real-world situations, allowing them to apply theoretical knowledge to practical, context-specific scenarios. Unlike traditional teaching methods that focus solely on theoretical concepts, case studies bridge the gap between theory and practice by presenting participants with authentic challenges or dilemmas encountered in professional settings. By analyzing these cases, participants gain valuable insights into how theoretical principles can be applied in practical contexts, deepening their understanding of the subject matter. Moreover, case studies foster critical thinking and problem-solving skills as participants are tasked with identifying relevant information, evaluating options, and making decisions to resolve the presented scenario. Additionally, case studies often stimulate lively discussions and debates among participants, encouraging collaboration and the exchange of diverse perspectives. Overall, case studies are highly effective in enhancing comprehension and problem-solving skills by providing participants with hands-on experience in grappling with real-world challenges within a supportive learning environment.

- **Practice by doing**

Practice by doing is a highly effective learning method that emphasizes active engagement and experiential learning (Morris, 2020). Unlike passive learning approaches, such as lectures or readings, practice by doing encourages participants to directly engage with the material through hands-on activities. This active involvement allows participants to apply theoretical concepts in real-time situations, reinforcing their understanding through direct

experience. By actively participating in tasks, exercises, or simulations, participants not only deepen their comprehension of the material but also develop practical skills that can be readily applied in their professional or academic endeavors. Furthermore, this method promotes a deeper level of engagement and retention compared to passive learning methods. When individuals actively participate in learning activities, they are more likely to remember and internalize the information they encounter. This is because the act of doing reinforces neural connections in the brain, solidifying learning and making it more durable over time.

- **Simulation or role-playing**

Simulation or role-playing exercises provide participants with immersive experiences in simulated scenarios, replicating real-world challenges within a controlled environment. By assuming specific roles or engaging in simulated situations, participants have the opportunity to apply their knowledge and skills in practical contexts, allowing them to experiment with different approaches and strategies. These exercises not only enhance participants' problem-solving abilities but also enable them to develop effective communication, decision-making, and leadership skills. Moreover, simulation or role-playing exercises offer a safe space for participants to make mistakes and learn from them without real-world consequences. This fosters a culture of experimentation and innovation, encouraging participants to explore alternative solutions and refine their approaches based on feedback and reflection (Russell and Shepherd, 2010)¹⁶.

- **Gamification**

Gamification revolutionizes traditional training methods by infusing game-like elements into learning activities, transforming them into interactive and engaging experiences. By leveraging principles of game design, such as challenges, rewards, competition, and progression, gamification motivates participants to actively participate in training sessions and strive toward achieving learning objectives. Through the incorporation of elements like points, badges, leaderboards, and levels, participants are incentivized to fully immerse themselves in the learning process, driving higher levels of engagement and participation. One of the key strengths of gamification is its ability to appeal to diverse learning styles and preferences. Whether participants are visual learners who benefit from interactive graphics, auditory learners who thrive on sound cues, or kinesthetics learners who prefer hands-on activities, gamification offers a versatile approach that caters to various learning modalities. By providing a dynamic and interactive learning environment, gamification captivates participants' attention and maintains their interest throughout the Training Programme, leading to higher levels of knowledge retention and

¹⁶ Russell, C., & Shepherd, J. (2010). Online role-play environments for higher education. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 41(6), 992-1002.

skill development (Kapp, 2012)¹⁷. To get further insights into this method's issue, trainers should ask themselves the following questions:

Which methods will best address participants' identified needs, the training objectives as well as the chosen topics for the training?

How will they apply a participatory and interactive methodology? Which interactive methods will they consider in their training?

How will they ensure that a training environment where the principles of participation and empowerment, accountability, non-discrimination and inclusion are respected?

Table 3. Overview of Recommended Methods

Training Methods	Advantages
Pre-readings	Provide essential background information and key concepts; allow deeper understanding; promote active learning
Short lectures	Concisely provide essential information; capture participants' attention; maintain engagement
Case Studies	Provide hands-on experience; bridge the gap between theory and practice; Foster critical thinking and problem-solving skills
Practice by doing	Allows to engage with hands-on experience; reinforces understanding through direct experience; Allows to develop practical skills
Simulation/Role-playing	Provides participants with immersive experiences in simulated scenarios; allows participants to apply their knowledge and skills in practical contexts; enhances participants' problem-solving abilities; allows participants to develop effective communication, decision-making, and leadership skills

¹⁷ Kapp, K. M. (2012). The gamification of learning and instruction: game-based methods and strategies for training and education. John Wiley & Sons.

Gamification	Motivates participants; appeals to diverse learning styles and preferences; captivates attention
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Step 7: Set up a Team

Consider trainer's educational background, educational skills, and diversity and ensure that all information regarding the training's participants, objectives and methods are shared with all trainers including support staff and eventual monitoring and evaluation staff.

Step 8: Identify and choose a monitoring and evaluation methodology and relevant methods and techniques

Both monitoring and evaluation are often done spontaneously by trainers by way of getting feedback from participants in terms of impressions along the implementation of training.

To get further insights into monitoring and evaluation, trainers should consider the following issues:

What does the evaluation aim for?

What are we interested in finding out?

Concerning these specific trainings and workshops though, there is an accountability requirement therefore, a necessity to carry out systematic monitoring and evaluation to measure their *effectiveness* and identify areas for improvement. This entails that both monitoring and evaluation are required to be backed by a more sophisticated methodology and should be carefully planned.

Developed by Don Kirkpatrick in 1959 and updated in 2006, Kirkpatrick's Taxonomy¹⁸ is perhaps the most widely used method of evaluating training effectiveness. This framework offers a four-level strategy that anyone can use to evaluate the effectiveness of any training course or programme. Simplicity and pragmatism of practice are the advantages of Kirkpatrick's model (Aliger and Janak, 1989)¹⁹.

The four levels of evaluation, namely are:

(1) Reaction which refers to the level of satisfaction of the participants to the training activities;

(2) Learning which refers to the change/improvement in Knowledge, Skill and Attitudes (see above mentioned three learning dimensions);

¹⁸ Donald L. Kirkpatrick and James D. Kirkpatrick, *Evaluating Training Programmes: The Four Levels*, 3rd ed. (San Francisco, California, Berrett-Koehler, 2006).

¹⁹ Alliger, G. M., & Janak, E. A. (1989). Kirkpatrick's levels of training criteria: Thirty years later. *Personnel psychology*, 42(2), 331-342.

(3) Transfer/Behaviour which refers to the improvement in the learners' behaviour and capability, and their implementation/application in their work context of what they have learned on the course (e.g., were they able to apply it in their work?) and

(4) Results/Impact which refers to the effects of the learning on the broader environment (e.g., have the learners, as a result of the training course, contributed to any changes in their communities?)

That has profound implications for monitoring and evaluation planning and design. To be able to carry out comprehensive monitoring and evaluation processes throughout the training activities under the AgroServ Training Programme, trainers will have to choose and plan for methods and techniques/combinations of various methods and techniques addressing all four evaluation levels, i.e., reaction, learning, transfer/behaviour and results/impact (Table 4).

Table 4. Kirkpatrick's Four Evaluation Levels²⁰

Levels	Aim: What does it measure?	Key questions	Methods & Techniques	Timing
1. REACTION	What learners thought and felt about the training course and about their learning	Are the participants satisfied with the training course? How do they intend to use the new knowledge?	Observation, daily feedback and debriefings, discussions with learners and facilitators	During and at the end of the training course
2. LEARNING	Increase in knowledge or capacity as a result of the training course	Did the participants learn what was intended when the training course was being designed?	Questionnaires, tests and activities, observation, role plays, peer assessment, self-assessment, etc.	At the end of a training course
3. BEHAVIOUR/ TRANSFER	How far the learners' behaviour has improved, and the extent to which they have been implementing/applying the learning (medium-term results)	Have the participants put what they learned into practice? Have they passed along their new knowledge to others in their	Follow-up questionnaires, focus groups, on-the-job observation, interviews with learners or learners'	At pre-determined intervals after a training course has taken place

²⁰ From Planning to Impact: A Manual on Human Rights Training Methodology (2020) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.18356/33ef5d5d-en>.

		organizations?	supervisors or other stakeholders, collection of impact stories, collection of learner's products (materials), follow-up sessions	(usually after 3 to 6 months)
4. IMPACT	The effect on the organization/ community/society resulting from the actions of the learners (long-term results)	Did the training course contribute to any broader changes in the organization/ community/society through the work of the learners?	Follow-up questionnaires, follow-up interviews with main stakeholders, on-the-job observation, organization performance records, media news, other reports	At pre-determined intervals after a training course has taken place (usually after 12 to 24 months)

In other words, assessing only the reaction of participants is, of course, an option but if the aim is to show training effectiveness, evaluation at the remaining three levels should be planned for especially, in terms of methods, techniques and time. An AgroServ Training Toolbox including a Registration and Needs Assessment Form, Templates for Training Programme, Training Agenda, an End of the Training Evaluation Form and a Follow-up Evaluation Form will shortly be available for trainers on the AgroServ Cloud.

7. Conclusion

This deliverable suggests a methodology and presents an 8 steps-guidelines on training planning and design for trainers under the AgroServ Training Programme.

This document provides a framework for the creation of participatory, engaging, impactful, and tailored training activities that effectively meet participants' needs.

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At the same time, the document also provides an evaluation framework for trainers in order for them to be able to assess if the training activities are producing the expected results in terms of knowledge, skills and attitudes/behaviors of training participants.

Indeed, the collection of material and feedback in terms of results from those training activities is crucial in view of providing, by the end of the AgroServ Project, a report on training activities (i.e., D5.5) trying to facilitate and optimise the implementation of Training Programmes of RI services for agroecology based on best practices.

To facilitate the above process, in order for trainers to be able to contribute to the harmonization of those activities in AgroServ, it is estimated that both the above-described methodological framework and guidelines including the evaluation framework therein, should be the subject of a training of trainers.

8. ANNEX:

Survey for WP Leaders and AMs on AgroServ Training Programme

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SURVEY

Welcome!

This survey is being conducted as part of the activities outlined in Work Package 5 of the AgroServ project. Specifically, Task 5.3 is dedicated to the creation of the AgroServ Training Programme and coordinating training services for key end-users from various work packages.

To accomplish this goal, we are seeking your input through this survey to evaluate the training sessions currently scheduled within the AgroServ project and to jointly assess the potential training requirements of our users.

As Access Managers and WP leaders, we kindly invite you to participate in this 20 min online survey!

Your answers will be treated in a strictly confidential manner and will be anonymised for aggregate statistical analysis.*

For any questions or technical problems, please contact

cavoski@iamb.it or spadavecchia@iamb.it

Deadline for completing the survey is 27 November 2023

Thank you very much for your valuable cooperation!

The WP5 Team

**Please note that personal data will be treated confidentially and in compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679*

Who are you?

1.1 Name of your Research Infrastructure*

1.2 Name of your institution *

1.3 In which WP are you involved?*

- WP1
- WP2
- WP3
- WP4
- WP5
- WP6
- WP7
- WP8
- WP9

1.4 What is your role in the AgroServ project?*

- RI Access Manager
- WP leader
- Both
- Other (please specify)

Assessing the planned training activities within AgroServ

1.5 Do you plan to implement any training activity within your WP?

- Yes
- No

1.6 If yes, when is the training activity planned?

e.g. Month, Year

1.7 Who is the intended audience?

1.8 What would be the training topic/s?

1.9 Would the training be on-line or face-to-face?

1.10 How long do you expect the training session will last?

(in hours)

1.11 Did you already identify the trainers?

- Yes
- No

1.12 If yes, who are they?

If possible, specify the first name, last name and e-mail

1.13 Do you plan to implement any training activity within your RI or Installations during TAs?

- Yes
- No

1.14 If yes, when is the training activity planned?

e.g. Month, Year

1.15 Who is the intended audience?

1.16 What would be the training topic/s?

1.17 Would the training be on-line or face-to-face?

1.18 How long do you expect the training session will last?

(in hours)

1.19 Did you already identify the trainers?

- Yes
- No

1.20 If yes, who are they?

If possible, specify the first name, last name, affiliation and e-mail

1.21 Could you share the specific URL leading to the training segment on your RI website?

Assessing User Training Needs within AgroServ

1.22 From your perspective as an AM or WP leader, what are the most common challenges or issues that users interested in AgroServ services would encounter?

1.23 Which skills or knowledge do you think users need to have before using AgroServ services?

1.24 Which skills or knowledge do you think users need to have in order to use AgroServ services efficiently?

1.25 Which training do you think installation managers should provide to users at installation level (e.g., lab security, how to use a specific tool or instrument)?

1.26 Is there anything else you would like to add or any other insights or suggestions related to user training needs (suggestions based on your previous experiences)?